

**POPULATION AGING AND SOCIOECONOMIC INEQUALITIES:
CHALLENGES TO LONG-TERM CARE AND LONG-TERM CARE
FACILITIES FOR THE ELDERLY IN BRAZIL**

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18633907

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ABSTRACT

With the objective of analyzing how population aging in Brazil reshapes the demand for Long-Term Care Institutions for Older Adults (Instituições de Longa Permanência para Idosos – ILPIs) and imposes new challenges on systems of long-term protection and care, this article is methodologically classified as a scoping review with a qualitative and theoretical-analytical approach, articulated with documentary research and guided by a critical socio-structural perspective. The results indicate that the country is undergoing an accelerated demographic transition: the proportion of individuals aged 65 years or older increased from 3.2% in 1970 to 10.9% in 2022, while the aging index rose from 7.7% to 55.1%. Projections suggest that, from 2029 onward, the number of older adults will surpass that of children, evidencing the consolidation of population aging. However, this process occurs in a profoundly unequal manner across socioeconomic strata: middle- and high-income households present aging indices above 200%, whereas groups living in extreme poverty do not reach 20%, revealing distinct trajectories in terms of health, labor participation, life expectancy, and family caregiving capacity. Furthermore, the low participation of older adults in the labor force—accounting for 19.7% of the working-age population but only 7.8% of the economically active population—heightens the risks of dependence and premature institutionalization.

Keywords: Aging. Long-Term Care Institutions. Socioeconomic Inequalities. Social Protection.

INTRODUCTION

Population aging is one of the most significant demographic phenomena of the 21st century and has led to profound reconfigurations in social protection systems, family dynamics, and public care policies (Horst; Stroparo, 2023). In Brazil, this process is occurring rapidly and in a disjointed manner, within a context marked by persistent socioeconomic inequalities. Between 2000 and 2023, the average age of the population increased from 28.3 to 35.5 years, with projections indicating that it should reach 48.4 years in 2070 (Leone, 2025). This trend results from the continuous decline in fertility, the increase in life expectancy, and the demographic transition that began in the country at the end of the 19th century.

The transformations in the age structure are evident: the proportion of people aged 65 or older increased from 3.2% in 1970 to 10.9% in 2022, while the aging index rose from 7.7% to 55.1% in the same period (Leone, 2025). Projections indicate that, from 2029 onwards, the number of elderly people should exceed the number of children under 15 years of age, which implies profound changes in the ways care is provided and in the demands on the State and families (Alves, 2022). Such changes put pressure on health, social security and social assistance systems, especially in the face of the growing incidence of chronic diseases and the increase in functional dependence (Horst; Stroparo, 2023; Stroparo, 2023).

However, population aging in Brazil is not occurring homogeneously. Studies show that socioeconomic inequalities shape distinct trajectories of living, illness, and aging (Escorcim, 2021; Camarano, 2018). Recent data indicate that middle- and high-income households already have aging rates exceeding 200%, while among groups in extreme poverty these rates do not reach 20%, revealing structural asymmetries in living conditions and access to care (Leone, 2025). These disparities are also reflected in the labor market: although people aged 60 or older represent 19.7% of the working-age population, they make up only 7.8% of the workforce, indicating economic vulnerability and an increased risk of dependency (Bichara; Costanzi, 2025).

In this scenario, Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (ILPIs) assume a central role in the care network, although they have historically operated under conditions of heterogeneity, underfunding, and insufficient regulation. The weakening of family networks, the reduction in household size, the intensification of women's paid work, and increased longevity reinforce the demand for formal and long-term care. However, Brazilian ILPIs face structural challenges, such as unequal territorial distribution, insufficient public funding, marked variations in the

quality of services, and a lack of systemic integration with health and social assistance policies (Wajnman; Oliveira; Oliveira, 2004; Horst; Stroparo, 2023; Stroparo, 2023).

Therefore, understanding how population aging, coupled with socioeconomic inequalities, reshapes the demand for long-term care facilities is fundamental for planning public policies that ensure dignified and equitable care. More than a demographic issue, it is an ethical, social, and institutional challenge that requires rethinking the role of the State and the organization of the long-term care system in Brazil.

Brazilian population aging has progressed rapidly and unevenly, representing one of the greatest contemporary challenges for social, health, and long-term care policies. In recent decades, the country has experienced a rapid decline in fertility, increased longevity, and structural changes in age composition, phenomena widely documented in demographic literature and official bodies (LEONE, 2025). In this transition, socioeconomic inequalities play a determining role: different social strata age unequally, presenting marked contrasts in health conditions, social protection, access to services, and capacity for home care. Recent research indicates that vulnerable elderly individuals tend to have greater functional dependence, less family support, and a higher probability of institutionalization (Pineiro et al., 2016; Hartwig et al., 2024; Horst; Stroparo, 2023; Stroparo, 2023).

Thus, inequalities accumulated throughout the life course increase the demand for long-term care and strain the existing institutional network. Although the institutionalization of care remains largely analog, the ongoing digital transformations in the State, in the management of social policies, and in health systems redefine response capacities, configure new types of socio-technical vulnerability, and highlight inequalities in the way older adults and long-term care facilities are incorporated into contemporary digitalization. This scenario reinforces the importance of critically analyzing inequalities in aging and the emerging challenges for social protection (Stroparo, 2021).

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Population aging is one of the most significant demographic phenomena of the 21st century, characterized by the rapid expansion of the elderly population in different social and territorial contexts. However, as Barros and Goldbaum (2019) point out, aging does not occur homogeneously: it is profoundly affected by inequalities accumulated throughout life, reflecting social stratification in health, income, education, work, and housing conditions.

These inequalities produce distinct aging profiles, with direct impacts on morbidity, functional dependence, and care needs.

Authors such as Leone (2025) highlight that longevity is associated with socioeconomic level: while higher-income groups reach older ages in better health conditions, poor populations experience earlier and more vulnerable aging, with a higher incidence of chronic diseases, frailty, and functional limitations. Epidemiological studies corroborate this pattern, demonstrating that morbidity, cardiovascular risk, dependency, and mortality vary according to social class and territory (Couto et al., 2017; Perreira; Jesus; Martins, 2020).

Unequal aging is also expressed through regional disparities. Lacerda et al. (2021) show that the distribution of Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (ILPIs) in the country demonstrates significant territorial gaps: 64% of municipalities have no such facility, creating an asymmetrical scenario of access to institutional care. This territorial imbalance intensifies social vulnerabilities, since regions with lower institutional supply coincide with low coverage of social and health services.

Furthermore, inequalities in family and community support networks directly influence the demand for care. In low-income groups, the absence of public policies on housing, health, and economic security, as analyzed by Silva and Galindo (2023), exacerbates functional dependence and reduces the capacity of families to provide home care. Thus, institutionalization often appears as an alternative for elderly people without social, family, and financial support.

Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (ILPIs) are residential spaces designed to accommodate people aged 60 or older who require support in activities of daily living, continuous care, or social protection. The most consolidated normative definition stems from ANVISA Resolution RDC No. 283/2005, which establishes minimum standards for physical structure, hygiene, human resources, food, record keeping, and care routines (BRAZIL, 2005). The regulation classifies residents into three profiles: independent, semi-dependent, and dependent, according to their need for assistance in activities of daily living, which determines the number of caregivers, the care structure, and the care plan.

The Statute of the Elderly (Law No. 10.741/2003) reinforces that institutionalization should be an exceptional measure, recommending that it only occur when there are no conditions for maintaining autonomy and safety in family life. The National Policy for the Elderly (Law No. 8.842/1994) defines shared responsibility between the State, family, and society in guaranteeing the well-being of the elderly population. In terms of social protection, the National Classification of Social Assistance Services defines institutional care as belonging

to a high-complexity level, requiring comprehensive conditions of housing, food, personal care, social interaction, and community ties.

Environmental issues also fall within the regulatory scope. Although there is no exclusive environmental standard for Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (ILPIs), many of them perform nursing procedures and are therefore subject to CONAMA Resolution No. 358/2005, which deals with the management and final disposal of healthcare waste. It is also important to highlight legislation regarding effluents, medication disposal, and sanitary standards, which directly impact the routine operations of these institutions.

In empirical terms, the literature demonstrates strong heterogeneity among public, philanthropic, and private long-term care facilities. Pinheiro et al. (2016) show that elderly people in non-profit long-term care facilities tend to have worse socioeconomic conditions and more comorbidities, while for-profit institutions, although with better infrastructure, often become economically inaccessible. Guimarães et al. (2023) corroborate this difference, identifying regional inequalities that affect physical structure, human resources, and quality of care.

Other operational challenges are identified by Oliveira and Silva (2023), who analyze gaps in oversight, lack of standardization, and difficulties in complying with regulations. In the post-pandemic context, studies such as Correa and Sperchi (2024) and Coutinho et al. (2023) show how long-term care facilities for the elderly (ILPIs) experienced crises exacerbated by a shortage of caregivers, increased costs, and insufficient government support. The complexity of healthcare costs in ILPIs, especially with caregivers and medications, makes current public funding insufficient to cover the expenses of elderly people with a higher degree of dependency, even in institutions where most residents have mild dependency (Horst; Stroparo, 2023; Stroparo, 2023).

The international debate on long - term care has highlighted the need for integrated systems that link health, social assistance, housing, and social protection. Barreira et al. (2023), in a comprehensive *umbrella review*, identify six central axes of this care: (1) continuous functional support, (2) intersectoral coordination, (3) sustainable financing, (4) workforce professionalization, (5) equitable access, and (6) monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.

In Latin American countries, Wachholz et al. (2024) show that institutionalization is still marked by the absence of robust public systems, informality of care, and chronic deficits in data, oversight, and funding. In the Brazilian case, Torres et al. (2020) highlight that, despite the advances of the SUS (Unified Health System) in elderly health care, the country does not have a national policy for long-term care, which generates fragmented care.

The literature shows that a large part of the demand for long-term care facilities arises precisely from the inadequacy of these policies. Classic and recent studies — Oliveira and Rozendo (2014); Campos et al. (2022); Pessôa et al. (2010) — indicate that families structured in fragile arrangements, with low income and little support network, find in long-term care facilities the only possible alternative for care.

Vulnerability is also present in accounts of institutionalization. Horst and Stroparo (2023) demonstrate that many elderly people arrive at long-term care facilities due to abandonment, inability to care for themselves, advanced illnesses, or the absence of family members able to provide care. Sposato, Morais, and Lage (2019) emphasize that institutionalization, in these cases, does not represent a choice, but an imposition of structural inequalities.

A significant portion of the literature emphasizes that long-term care facilities have become important social protection mechanisms, especially for poor elderly people. Barreira et al. (2023) reinforce that long-term care systems should integrate social and health services, as well as income and housing policies—areas traditionally neglected for the elderly in Brazil.

From an economic standpoint, studies such as Horst and Stroparo (2023) and Stroparo, Eidam, and Czaikovski (2020) indicate that healthcare costs represent a significant portion of institutional expenses, putting pressure on the budgets of long-term care facilities and impacting the quality of care. These findings reinforce the need for permanent funding, support mechanisms, and structured public policies.

Finally, institutional violence also appears in the literature. Poltronieri, Souza and Ribeiro (2019) analyze that long-term care policies incorporate violence prevention mechanisms, closely linked to guaranteeing the dignity, physical integrity and autonomy of residents.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a qualitative, exploratory, and theoretical-analytical approach, structured from a *Scoping Review*, articulated with documentary research and critical analysis of the literature on population aging, socioeconomic inequalities, long-term care, and Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (LTCFs).

Scoping *reviews* were selected for their suitability to broad, complex, and multidimensional themes. According to Arksey and O'Malley (2005), it is a review method that aims to "examine the extent, scope, and nature of research on a topic, with the goal of mapping

concepts, evidence, and gaps in the literature." The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI, 2020) adds that this type of review is particularly indicated when the objective is to clarify concepts, identify knowledge gaps, and synthesize evidence comprehensively, especially in fields where studies present methodological diversity. Unlike traditional systematic reviews, *scoping reviews* do not require critical evaluation of the quality of studies, allowing the integration of empirical and theoretical articles, normative documents, and institutional reports, which aligns with the interdisciplinary nature of this investigation.

The review was conducted following the five methodological steps proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005), refined by Levac, Colquhoun and O'Brien (2010): (1) formulation of the guiding question; (2) identification of relevant studies and documents; (3) selection of material according to inclusion and exclusion criteria; (4) extraction and thematic categorization of data; (5) synthesis and presentation of results.

Figure 1. Methodological Steps

Source: Prepared by the authors using the Napkin tool (2025).

The guiding question established was: "How does unequal population aging influence the demand for Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly, and what challenges emerge for care and social protection?"

A literature search was conducted in the SciELO, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases, as well as government repositories. The following descriptors in Portuguese and English were used: *population aging*, *social inequalities*, *institutionalization of the elderly*, *long-term care facilities*, *long-term care*, *aging and inequality*, *care systems*. Inclusion criteria included: (a) studies published between 2010 and 2025; (b) peer-reviewed articles; (c) normative documents and official reports related to long-term care facilities and long-term care. Duplicate studies, abstracts without full text, and publications outside the thematic scope were excluded.

Simultaneously, documentary research was carried out, encompassing key legislation and regulations for the operation of ILPIs, such as: Law No. 8.842/1994 (Policy The National Law for the Elderly (Law No. 10.741/2003 - Statute of the Elderly); ANVISA Resolution RDC No. 283/2005; National Classification of Social Assistance Services; and CONAMA Resolution No. 358/2005, pertaining to the management of healthcare waste. These documents were analyzed regarding institutional definition, structural requirements, care standards, regulations, and state responsibilities.

After selecting and reading the sources in full, thematic categorization was carried out, according to JBI (2020) guidelines, resulting in the following analytical axes: (1) socioeconomic inequalities and aging profiles; (2) care, organizational and territorial demands of long-term care facilities; (3) challenges of care and social protection in contexts of unequal aging.

Finally, an interpretative synthesis was carried out, integrating empirical evidence, theoretical foundations, and regulatory frameworks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A Scoping Review identified three major analytical axes regarding the relationship between unequal aging, institutionalization, and challenges in long-term care: (1) socioeconomic inequalities and differentiated aging profiles; (2) dynamics of demand and functioning of long-term care facilities; and (3) contemporary challenges of care and social protection. Before delving deeper into these axes, Table 1 presents a summary of the selected

studies, including authors, objectives, methodologies, and main findings, in order to highlight the heterogeneity of scientific production and the patterns identified in the literature.

Table 1 – Summary of studies included in the Scoping Review on Long-Term Care Facilities and Inequalities in Aging

Author(s)	Objective	Methodology	Main finding
Pinheiro et al. (2016)	Comparing profiles of elderly people in for-profit and non-profit long-term care facilities.	Descriptive study using institutional data	Elderly people in non-profit long-term care facilities presented worse socioeconomic and health conditions.
Guimarães et al. (2023)	Evaluating Brazilian Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (ILPIs) according to a multidimensional model of quality and regional inequalities.	Ecological study using data from the 2018 SUAS Census (1,665 institutions)	Long-term care facilities in the North/Northeast region showed inferior performance in terms of staff, infrastructure, and care.
Lacerda et al. (2021)	Mapping the geospatial distribution of long-term care facilities.	Municipal geospatial study	64% of municipalities do not have long-term care facilities, revealing significant gaps in healthcare services.
Silva-Souza et al. (2025)	Discussing public policies, coverage, and challenges of long-term care facilities for the elderly.	Analytical study with literature review	The need for integrated long-term care policies.
Silva et al. (2021)	Evaluate institutional performance using monitoring indicators.	Quantitative study in 41 long-term care facilities.	Low caregiver-to-resident ratio and high occupancy rate.
Hartwig et al. (2024)	To identify the demographic and socioeconomic profile of institutionalized elderly people.	Narrative review	Predominantly elderly individuals with multiple comorbidities and low income.
Quinteiro & Rodrigues (2022)	Assessing the impact of the physical environment on quality of life.	Systematic review	The physical and structural conditions of long-term care facilities influence well-being.
Soares, Silva & Ribeiro (2021)	To analyze the impacts of COVID-19 on the management of long-term care facilities.	Reflective study + document analysis	The pandemic exacerbated pre-existing shortcomings: staff shortages, weak regulations, and underfunding.
Stroparo (2024)	To analyze structural, organizational, and ethical challenges in long-term care facilities for the elderly.	Critical analytical study	It revealed a structural deficit, insufficient funding, and precarious working conditions.
Stroparo, Eidam & Czaikowski (2020)	Analyze operational costs and implications for care.	Applied qualitative study	Healthcare/medication costs are the most significant and affect the quality of care.

Source: Survey Data, (2025)

Analysis of the literature demonstrates that population aging occurs in a profoundly unequal manner, revealing divergent profiles according to social class, territory, education, and

living conditions. Studies by Barros and Goldbaum (2019) and Leone (2025) indicate that older adults with lower incomes have a higher prevalence of chronic diseases, early functional dependence, less family support, and precarious housing conditions—factors that increase the likelihood of institutionalization.

National and regional research reinforces this pattern. Couto et al. (2017) identified an association between cardiovascular risk, low education level, and poorer quality of life, while Ferreira, Jesus, and Martins (2020) describe differentiated patterns of elderly mortality in the Northeast, directly related to social determinants of health.

Inequality is also expressed territorially. Lacerda et al. (2021) showed that approximately 64% of Brazilian municipalities do not have any long-term care facilities, creating gaps in care, mainly in the North and Northeast regions. This unequal distribution limits access to institutional care, especially in small and rural municipalities, with less capacity to offer public services and less presence of philanthropic institutions.

Thus, the literature converges on the understanding that inequalities accumulated throughout the life course produce more vulnerable aging trajectories, with a greater chance of institutionalization and less autonomy, especially among poor, Black, female, and elderly residents of peripheral territories.

Research reveals that the demand for long-term care facilities has grown consistently, driven by demographic transformations, family changes, fragile socioeconomic conditions, and the absence of home care policies. The reasons that lead to institutionalization include family abandonment, lack of caregivers, disabling illnesses, functional dependence, and insecurity at home (Stroparo, 2024).

The review also highlights heterogeneity among public, private, and philanthropic institutions. Pinheiro et al. (2016) identified profound differences in the profile of residents according to the type of institution: non-profit long-term care facilities concentrate elderly people with lower income and greater dependency, while private long-term care facilities serve less vulnerable profiles, but are inaccessible to most of the elderly population. Guimarães et al. (2023) expand this debate by demonstrating significant regional disparities in structural quality, human resources, infrastructure, and care practices.

Furthermore, the literature shows that current regulations — especially RDC No. 283/2005, the Statute of the Elderly, and the National Classification of the SUAS (Unified Social Assistance System) — establish minimum operating standards, but many institutions face difficulties in complying with them. Oliveira and Silva (2023) point out that oversight is insufficient and unequal, contributing to heterogeneity in care conditions.

Environmental issues also emerge as a challenge. Long-term care facilities that perform nursing procedures are subject to CONAMA Resolution No. 358/2005, concerning the management of healthcare waste, which implies additional structural and operational requirements.

Based on this evidence, it is observed that the demand for long-term care facilities is directly associated with social inequalities and the inadequacy of public policies that promote autonomy, community care, and family support.

Studies produced by Stroparo (2024) deepen this diagnosis by demonstrating that the daily functioning of long-term care facilities is marked by financial constraints, insufficient physical infrastructure, high worker turnover, and weaknesses in care management, aspects that are aggravated in small institutions located in municipalities with low fiscal capacity. The author also highlights that, even with current regulations, many institutions operate with minimal resources, which compromises full compliance with RDC No. 283/2005.

The literature reviewed shows that Brazil lacks a national long-term care system, which leads to fragmented care and overburdening of long-term care facilities. International studies, such as Barreira et al. (2023) and Wachholz et al. (2024), indicate that Latin American countries face similar challenges: lack of public funding, informality of care, scarcity of data, and insufficient intersectoral policies.

In the Brazilian context, the COVID-19 pandemic exposed historical fragilities. Correa and Sperchi (2024), Coutinho et al. (2023), and Kevern et al. (2020) describe devastating impacts: high mortality, extreme isolation, lack of protective equipment, illness among the workforce, and scarcity of government support. These vulnerabilities increased the operational costs of long-term care facilities and strained their financial sustainability.

In this sense, economic studies by Horst and Stroparo (2023) and Stroparo, Eidam and Czaikovski (2020) show that health costs are the most significant in the institutional budget, directly affecting the quality of care offered. This implies the need for continuous funding policies and recognition of long-term care facilities as a formal part of the social protection network.

The literature also addresses ethical and human rights dimensions. Poltronieri, Souza, and Ribeiro (2019) analyze that institutional violence—physical, psychological, or neglectful—remains a risk in environments with low oversight, scarce resources, and reduced staff, indicating an urgent need to consolidate care practices centered on dignity and autonomy.

The economic analysis of institutionalization carried out by Stroparo, Eidam, and Czaikovski (2020) reveals that costs related to healthcare, medications, specialized care, and

care materials constitute the largest portion of the institutional budget, representing a critical factor for the financial sustainability of long-term care facilities. These high costs directly impact the quality of care, especially in philanthropic institutions that depend on donations and volunteer work. The research shows that chronic resource insufficiency compromises strategies for promoting quality of life, limiting therapeutic activities, building maintenance, and the acquisition of essential supplies.

Finally, the reflections of Guerra et al. (2024) and Torres et al. (2020) reinforce that public policies for the elderly remain fragmented between health, social assistance and social security, without intersectoral articulation capable of guaranteeing a solid network of support and continued care.

The results, therefore, reveal that: unequal aging is a structuring determinant of institutionalization; long-term care facilities emerge as a response to the inadequacy of social policies and the fragility of family networks; territorial and socioeconomic inequalities shape both the supply and access to institutions; structural challenges—funding, oversight, workforce, health standards—compromise the quality of care; the absence of a national long-term care system exacerbates vulnerabilities; existing public policies are insufficient to address the magnitude of demographic transformations.

Thus, institutionalization, when not anchored in a state network, tends to reproduce pre-existing inequalities, reinforcing the urgent need for structured and intersectoral policies of care and social protection.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This Scoping Review, which aimed to analyze how population aging and socioeconomic inequalities influence the demand for Long-Term Care Facilities for the Elderly (LTCFs) and what challenges emerge for care and social protection, demonstrates that aging, although a universal process, is experienced in a profoundly unequal way. These inequalities, accumulated throughout the life course, shape differentiated trajectories of vulnerability, influencing both the risk of institutionalization and the conditions under which it occurs.

The literature reviewed shows that institutionalization in long-term care facilities is frequently the result of structural deficiencies—fragile family networks, absence of formal long-term care policies, and economic limitations—and not just individual choices. These institutions, in turn, operate in a context marked by underfunding, increasing demand for complex care, workforce shortages, and difficulties in complying with regulations such as RDC

No. 283/2005 and CONAMA Resolution No. 358/2005. Studies such as those by Stroparo (2024) and Stroparo, Eidam, and Czaikovski (2020) reinforce that healthcare costs represent the most significant portion of the institutional budget, directly affecting the quality of care offered.

Additionally, the lack of a national long-term care system exacerbates the fragmentation between health, social assistance, and social security, hindering the construction of integrated support networks for older people. In a scenario of marked territorial inequalities and high institutional heterogeneity, precariousness tends to intensify, especially in philanthropic long-term care facilities and in smaller municipalities.

Given this body of evidence, it is reaffirmed that addressing the challenges associated with aging requires structural public policies that recognize care as a fundamental social right. This implies expanding public funding, strengthening institutional capacity, ensuring effective oversight, improving the training and recognition of teams, and consolidating intersectoral social protection systems capable of responding to the growing needs of the elderly population.

Thus, the results indicate that building universal, equitable, and territorially sensitive long-term care is an indispensable condition for aging to be experienced with dignity, autonomy, and social justice. Strengthening long-term care facilities for the elderly (ILPIs), coupled with the creation of a national care system, represents a strategic and urgent step to ensure the protection and quality of life of older people in a context of profound demographic and social transformations.

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